

CORAS - User Guide

Disclaimer

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CORAS

CORAS training material can be found online, as well as is the book *'Model-Driven Risk Analysis: The CORAS Approach'* [1] which presents a comprehensive explanation of the CORAS approach. A chapter from the book called *"A Guided Tour of the CORAS Method"* [2] is available for free and introduces the method and language at an introductory level. In addition, a video explaining the interface can be found on Youtube [3].

In this document we present the tool interface alongside a simple example to demonstrate how the interface is utilized. The interface consists of three main components, in addition to a small menu for loading and saving diagrams. These three components are the *Canvas* and *Editor menu* which are apparent upon entering the website as well as the *Element Editor* which appears when selecting a diagram element.

Figure 1: CORAS tool interface.

The canvas is the main element of the editor and is where the diagram is drawn. Items from the editor menu are dragged and dropped on to the canvas. Once on the canvas the element editor menu can be displayed by right clicking on the element. This is where the diagram element can be modified, text can be added, and size can be changed. The element editor will present the user with a field for each attribute of the element that can be altered. For instance, an unwanted incident will contain a larger number of input fields than a vulnerability.

Figure 2: Interface with Element editor.

At the top of the canvas there are several tabs, one for each diagram type included in the CORAS method. When modeling according to the CORAS method the user would ideally create one diagram in each tab, from asset diagram to treatment overview. Each diagram would serve as part of the input to the next diagram to be made. The diagrams are ordered from left to right according to this process with the *Asset* diagram representing the assets which the risk assessment is performed to protect and the relationship between these assets. The *Threat diagram* is used to identify, estimate and evaluate risk. It is usually the diagram in which most of the effort is spent. The *Risk diagram* is used to show the results of the risk assessment in a clearer manner by stripping the detail from the threat diagram and just showing the risks alongside their threat source. The *Treatment diagram* is a threat diagram with treatments added and the *Treatment overview diagram* is a risk diagram with treatments added, in other words, the risk diagram is a simplified version of the threat diagram where the treatment overview diagram is the simplified version of the treatment diagram. These versions are useful for communicating the results of the risk assessment.

Most users, however, would likely not need to concern themselves with every tab, and can comfortably work with the asset diagrams and threat diagrams. The only difference between tabs are the elements shown in the editor menu, where elements not relevant to the current diagram type are not shown. Any diagram can be loaded in any tab however, and diagrams can thus be copied to a more relevant tab as the process moves along. For example, when threats have been identified and evaluated, the user can copy the finished threat diagram into the treatment diagram tab where they can identify and add treatments.

The editor menu as mentioned contains all the elements which can be used in the current diagram type. In addition to this, there is a button on the right to turn on indicators, as well as tabs in the upper left which is used for *change management*. *Indicators* are any piece of information which can indicate a change in risk level and are an extension of CORAS that the user can turn on if desired.

Figure 3: Interface with Indicator.

Change management refers to utilizing CORAS models to model change to a system. It is a slightly more advanced feature of the modeling language and includes two additional views, depicted by visual changes to the elements. The *before* tab denotes elements of the model which are present only *before* the change is added. These elements will be removed due to the change. Note that visually these elements are unchanged from the default view when change management is not present. *Before-after* are elements which will persist through the change, in other words they exist both before and after. These elements are represented with a white shadow of the icon beneath to the left. Finally, in the *after* category we find elements which are introduced during the change itself. This can be additions or modifications to the system which must be represented in the model. This category is represented by icons with black shadows under the icons.

Example case

To demonstrate how to use the tool in the context of a risk assessment we will present a small example, using a simplified excerpt from the NEMECYS case study used in the integration section. The risk is an adversary accessing personal data by means of accessing a SD card on the SmartBox.

As CORAS is an asset centric risk assessment method, the first step is to identify the assets on which behalf we will conduct the risk assessment. In other words, the assets we intend to protect. This is done during the context establishment and documented as assets diagrams. Select the leftmost tab above the canvas and drag a stakeholder onto the canvas. After this, select the correct asset type from the menu and drop them above the stakeholder element. The element types are *direct* and *indirect*. An indirect asset is an asset which is not directly impacted by an unwanted incident but rather by harm to other assets, while a direct asset can be directly impacted. With the assets in place, we now determine their relationships. An arrow between two elements means that the receiving element is negatively impacted by harm to the former. For example, if confidentiality of sensitive information is impacted by an unwanted incident, the indirect asset *reputation* might be harmed as well.

Figure 4: Interface with asset diagram.

With the asset diagram done, we switch to the threat diagram tab. This is where most of the work on identifying risk is done, and where most risk assessors will spend the majority of their time. In this case we are concerned about a hacker accessing the SD card on our device. As this is a malicious risk, we tend to work from left to right, meaning that we imagine our threat source, in this case the hacker, and how they may work their way forward to an eventual unwanted incident. This initial step is shown in the image below.

Figure 5: Threat modeling first step.

Should the hacker get access to the SD card, they may use this to access data on the card. To show this, we create a new element describing this scenario and link it to the preceding threat scenario.

Figure 6: Threat modeling second step.

Finally, should the hacker get access to the data on the card, they may attempt to extract that data. This is an unwanted incident, as it impacts our asset; the confidentiality of personal data.

The preceding scenarios; while unwanted, do not directly harm an asset we have considered in this risk assessment.

Figure 7: Threat modeling third step.

Finally, we link the unwanted incident to its asset, thus creating our first risk. A risk is a combination of likelihood and consequence, and in this case would be the likelihood of the hacker extracting data from the SD card combined with the consequence of that happening.

Figure 8: Threat modeling fourth step.

While vulnerabilities can be identified at any time during this process, often to great benefit, for the purpose of illustration we add them now. We notice that this risk hinges on the hacker getting access to the SD card. This implies that the SD card or the device in which it is placed is vulnerable to a malicious adversary. To represent this, we place a vulnerability on the initializing link. This shows that there is a vulnerability present that allows for or increases the risk of this risk being initialized. Since this vulnerability is represented on the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) we add the CWE number as well, but this is not required.

Figure 9: Threat modeling fifth step.

We also note that the SD card or selected data on may be protected by authentication, for example basic password protection. To represent that lacking or poor authentication measures is necessary to get access to the data we add the vulnerability Improper authentication.

Figure 10: Threat modeling sixth step.

Finally, the data may also be encrypted, stopping an attacker from accessing the cleartext data. Since we consider the asset to represent legible information, accessing the encrypted data would not be considered an unwanted incident in this case as confidentiality would not be impacted. To represent this, we add the final vulnerability Inadequate encryption strength which points out that inadequate or missing encryption increases the risk of the hacker accessing the data on the SD card leading to the hacker extracting personal data.

Figure 11: Threat modeling seventh step.

As the last step on the threat diagram tab, we can add indicators. These can also be added at any point during the process and can unlike other elements be attached to anything. These elements are useful to add more information to the model that is not captured by the other elements, and plays a role during the risk calculation by modifying the value of whichever element they are attached to. In this case, we want to know more about how easy it is for an individual to get access to the SD card. A way of doing this can be to check the access control policy of the organization owning the SD card. The result of this query will then affect how present or significant vulnerability is. Likewise, we want to know which encryption algorithm is used if any. This will likewise affect the significance of the related vulnerability and modify the estimated chance of the threat propagating.

Figure 12: Threat modeling eighth step.

References

- [1] Model-Driven Risk Analysis – The CORAS approach. Lund, Solhaug, Stølen: <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783642123221> Atle Refsdal, Bjørnar Solhaug, Ketil Stølen. Cyber-Risk Management. Springer 2015.
- [2] Chapter 3 - A Guided Tour of the CORAS Method, Stølen, Lund, Solhaug, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287673426_A_Guided_Tour_of_the_CORAS_Method
- [3] CORAS video tutorial, https://youtu.be/DVZNV3S_9gA